

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART IV. SEPARATION FROM URANIUM

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Separation of thorium from uranium by the classical oxalic acid method is not satisfactory in that the ignited oxide is slightly coloured. *m*-Nitrobenzoic acid and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid are shown to give highly satisfactory results in the presence of 50 to 60 times of uranium in a second precipitation.

Dutt (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 75) from a critical study of the various methods for the separation of thorium from uranium, concluded that the oxalic acid method gave accurate results in U/Th ratio up to 200. Ryan, McDonell and Beamish (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1947, 19, 410) employed Ferron with success up to U/Th ratio of 2; when, however, larger amounts of uranium were present, a double precipitation was necessary and the thorium recovery was only 90%. Our experiments indicated that although from the consideration of ThO₂ weighed the oxalic acid method was unsatisfactory, the oxide residue left on ignition was coloured pale yellow even at small U/Th ratio and a pure *white* residue could be obtained only on a second precipitation. On account of the difficulty in dissolving the oxalate, a second precipitation presents a particular disadvantage. In this investigation *m*-nitrobenzoic acid and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid have been employed with the same success, and with the advantage that the precipitate is easily soluble in mineral acids. Although satisfactory results were obtained in a single precipitation, the residue showed always a slight yellow tinge, which certainly pointed to contamination by uranium. The amount of uranium, thus carried, however, was very small, a fraction of a milligram, and tests for thorium in the filtrate were negative. Thus, for most purposes of assay of uranium minerals for thorium, a single precipitation will be sufficient.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Reagents.—Pure thorium nitrate solution was prepared in the manner already reported (vide Part I in this series, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457). The thorium content of this solution was estimated with oxalic acid and *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (10 ml. of the solution gave 0.0567 g. and 0.0568 g. of ThO₂ respectively).

A sample of pure uranium oxide (Merck) was dissolved in nitric acid and crystallised twice from distilled water. The crystals on desiccation were weighed and dissolved in water. The U₃O₈ content was checked by

precipitation with redistilled (CO_2 free) ammonia and ignition; 10 ml. of the solution gave 0.1116 g. of U_3O_8 as against 0.1117 g. theoretical. Measured volumes of the two solutions were mixed for obtaining different U/Th ratios.

Preliminary investigation indicated that uranium was co-precipitated by both the reagents at a p_{H} above 3.5, and below 2.6 the precipitation of thorium was incomplete. All the following separations were carried out in the p_{H} range of 2.6 to 2.8, a condition which was easily established by thymol blue imparting a slightly red tinge

Procedure.—The p_{H} was adjusted to the proper value by making the solution just orange to thymol blue. The thorium was then precipitated from hot, nearly boiling solution and washed with a dilute solution of the reagent. For a second precipitation the precipitate was dissolved in hot dilute nitric acid,

TABLE I

Separation with m-nitrobenzoic acid.

Expt. No.	ThO_2 taken.	U_3O_8 added.	ThO_2 found.	Difference.	Remarks.
A. Single precipitation.					
1	0.0568 g.	0.1116 g.	0.0574 g.	-0.0006 g.	Residue colored slightly yellow in all cases.
2	0.0568	0.1116	0.0572	+0.0004	
3	0.0568	0.2232	0.0579	+0.0011	
B. Double precipitation.					
1	0.0568 g.	0.2232 g.	0.0568 g.	0	Residue white.
2	0.0568	0.5580	0.0569	+0.0001	
3	0.0568	1.1160	0.0572	+0.0004	
4	0.0568	3.3120	0.0572	+0.0004	
5	0.0142	0.1658	0.0142	0	
6	0.0284	0.1658	0.0283	-0.0001	
7	0.0284	0.3356	0.0283	-0.0001	

o-Chlorobenzoic Acid.—The procedure is similar to precipitation with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid.

TABLE II

Separation with o-chlorobenzoic acid.

Expt. No.	ThO_2 taken.	U_3O_8 added.	ThO_2 found.	Difference.	Remarks
Single precipitation.					
1	0.0583 g.	0.1116 g.	0.0581 g.	-0.0002 g.	Residue colored yellow.
2	0.0568	0.2232	0.0573	+0.0005	
3	0.0568	0.2232	0.0569	+0.0001	

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ taken.	U ³ O ₈ added.	ThO ₂ found.	Difference.
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B. Double precipitation.

4	0.0568	0.2232	0.0568	0
5	0.0568	0.5580	0.0568	0
6	0.0568	0.9926	0.0568	0
7	0.0568	0.4815	0.0567	-0.0001
8	0.0284	0.1240	0.0283	-0.0001
9	0.0284	0.2480	0.0285	+0.0001
10	0.0142	0.1240	0.0141	-0.0001
11	0.0142	0.2480	0.0142	0

It is thus evident that uranium in concentration up to 60 times that of thorium can conveniently be removed in a double precipitation by either *m*-nitrobenzoic acid or *o*-chlorobenzoic acid in the ρ_H range of 2.6 to 2.8.

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Received May 19, 1950.